

"Biomedical Engineering" in the Modern Healthcare System

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Abstract: This article discusses the development factors of biomedical engineering in the modern health care system and the problems in this direction.

Keywords: Biomedical engineering, Bioengineering, medical and technical research, infections and viruses, genetics, scientific laboratory of phytovirology, magnetic resonance imaging.

Biomedical technological innovations are the most demanding field in the modern scientific and economic world. Over the past decade, biomedicine has attracted the attention of investors around the world. According to experts, biotechnologies that contribute to the improvement of human life or organism may be one of the rapidly developing areas in the future. Therefore, it is very important to study the innovative problems of biomedical engineering and its development prospects, a new approach to the training of specialists in this field, and the implementation of priority scientific and research work in the field.

Today, the current problems and prospects of the development of the main directions of biomedical engineering are focused on the following - the role and importance of fundamental and practical medical and technical research and development, which are important elements of the development and improvement of the effectiveness of medical and technical research, the national health care system, modern achievements of medical science, rehabilitation industry, bionanosystems and bionanotechnologies of biomedical research, micro and nanorobots, medical microsystems, biological wave effects on the human body, non-invasive diagnostic methods.

Biomedical engineers work closely with physicians and others who provide health care to develop devices that directly affect the quality and length of human and animal life.

It should be said that we have good scientific and technical potential in this direction: there are institutes and universities engaged in this. But, unfortunately, it is almost impossible to get out of research and commercialize due to the lack of industrial enterprises in the industry. The decision stipulates the adoption of complex measures for the development of this sector.

We consider biological threats not only as infections and viruses dangerous to humans, but also as agricultural crop diseases, including genetically modified organisms and their control. In order to solve these problems and implement a unified state policy, the Council of Biological Safety was established under the Cabinet of Ministers. In addition, a scientific laboratory of phytovirology will appear for the first time in Uzbekistan. Also, measures to support foreign scientific centers to be opened for conducting scientific research in Uzbekistan were determined. Special grants are allocated for them from the Ministry of

Innovative Development.

Bioengineering or biomedical engineering is a science that advances knowledge in engineering, biology, and medicine and improves human health. Biomedical engineers combine their knowledge of biology and medicine with engineering principles and practices to develop devices and procedures that solve medical and health problems.

We can define the term biomedical engineer as follows.

A biomedical engineer is a professional who uses the latest medical research to create devices and programs that improve human health. The technologies being created are providing direct service in hospitals, laboratories, and rehabilitation centers.

Result: According to estimates, the global biotechnology market will reach \$2 trillion in 2025. Currently, this field is one of the fastest growing fields along with the IT field.

One of the rapidly developing directions in the world is biotechnology, which connects research achievements and the production process. Thanks to them, modern methods of plant protection, biodegradable polymers, ecological technologies were created. In order to develop this segment, the head of state signed the decision "On comprehensive measures to develop biotechnologies and improve the country's biological safety system".

Summary: Systems and products such as artificial organs, prostheses (artificial devices that replace missing body parts), instruments, medical information systems, health care management and service systems, along with most medical scientists conducts research for development and evaluation. Biomedical engineers may also design devices used in various medical procedures, imaging systems such as magnetic resonance imaging (mri), and devices to automate insulin injections or control bodily functions.

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